

Doublet Spin State Mediated Photoluminescence Upconversion in Organic Radical Donor-Triplet Acceptor Dyads

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ABSTRACT:

Donor-acceptor dyads are promising materials for improving triplet-sensitized photon upconversion due to faster intramolecular energy transfer (ET), which unfortunately competes with charge transfer (CT) dynamics. To circumvent the issue associated with CT, we propose a novel purely organic donor-acceptor dyad, where the CT character is confined within the donor moiety. In this work, we report the synthesis and characterization of a stable organic radical donor-triplet acceptor dyad (**TTM-Cz-Per**) consisting of the acceptor perylene (**Per**) linked to the donor (4-*N*-carbazolyl-2,6-dichlorophenyl)bis(2,4,6-trichlorophenyl)methyl radical (**TTM-Cz**). Upon red-excitation of **TTM-Cz-Per**, the doublet emission of the donor (**TTM-Cz**) is significantly quenched, and a recorded delayed emission centered at ca. 490 nm was attributed to the fluorescence emission from the **Per** acceptor. Time-resolved transient absorption spectroscopy suggests doublet-to-triplet energy transfer (DTET) dynamics from the donor to the acceptor as the time constant τ for the donor transient species decreases from 21.47 ns for the **TTM-Cz** sensitizer to 8.73 ns for **TTM-Cz-Per** dyad. This process is accompanied by the appearance of a long-lived component with $\tau = 97.06$ ns, which we ascribe to the triplet transient of the acceptor **Per**. Furthermore, computational results indicate that the DTET is intramolecular as computed spin densities of the quartet state show unpaired electrons of $\rho \approx 1$ on the **TTM-Cz** donor and of $\rho \approx 2$ on the acceptor **Per**. The present study highlights the possibility to employ doublet chromophoric systems for light-harvesting and energy upconversion, which can be further tailored for several optoelectronic applications.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Triplet-triplet annihilation photon upconversion (TTA-UC) is a nonlinear photophysical process that converts low-energy photons into higher-energy photons via the “fusion” of two triplet excitons into one high-energy excited singlet and a ground state singlet.¹ Compared to other upconversion methods, TTA-UC is attractive due to its ability to operate with low excitation intensities and noncoherent light sources.² It is because of this that TTA-UC has been tailored for applications such as solar energy conversion³⁻⁷ and photocatalysis.⁸⁻¹⁴

Conventionally, TTA-UC is achieved through the use bichromophoric systems consisting of a triplet donor/sensitizer and acceptor/emitter. Upon photoirradiation, the donor is excited from its singlet ground state (S_0) to its singlet excited state(s) before undergoing intersystem crossing (ISC) to populate its triplet manifolds. Through a Dexter energy transfer (ET) mechanism¹⁵, more specifically a triplet-triplet energy transfer (TTET), the donor transfers its excitation energy to the acceptor, resulting in the donor returning to its ground state and the acceptor being promoted to its triplet excited state. Two triplet-excited acceptors can then undergo TTA to produce one higher energy singlet-excited acceptor and one ground-state acceptor. The singlet excited acceptor then undergoes radiative decay to its ground state, emitting an upconverted photon (Figure 1a). Given the nature of this process, several aspects need to be considered when trying to maximize upconversion quantum yield (Φ_{UC}).

In most cases, the chromophoric samples used in TTA-UC are carefully deaerated to prevent quenching by molecular oxygen.¹⁶ Alternatively, the chromophoric mixtures can be frozen in rigid matrices to reduce diffusional quenching. Not only does quenching by molecular oxygen decrease the efficiency of the underlying photophysical processes, *viz.*, TET, TTA, and Φ_{UC} , but the quenching could also generate singlet oxygen (1O_2) which can compromise acene acceptors (e.g.

anthracenes) present in the sample, limiting the use of some of those chromophores under ambient conditions.¹⁷

a) Classical TTA-UC using donor and acceptor systems

b) Prior work from our group using donor-acceptor dyads

c) This Work

Figure 1. Jablonski diagrams illustrating a) traditional TTA-UC systems using separate donors and acceptors, b) charge transfer in prior dyads made by our lab, and c) our hypothesis of TTM-Cz based dyads for TTA-UC.

Furthermore, for an efficient Dexter ET to occur, there needs to be maximum wavefunction overlap between the donor and the acceptor, as well as the metastable triplet-excited acceptors when they undergo self-quenching. Hence, to achieve efficient ET and TTA, one must select donors and acceptors with sufficiently long triplet-state lifetimes so that diffusional-based ET can occur;¹⁸ however, this can also be addressed by tethering the donor and acceptor(s) together to create donor-acceptor (D-A) dyads. In recent years, several groups have reported D-A dyads that exhibit different degrees of complexities and photophysics.^{19–22} D-A dyads allow for rapid intramolecular ET between the donor and acceptor, which improves the efficiency of said ET. Prior work in our lab on D-A dyads for TTA-UC has revealed, however, that in addition to intramolecular ET, charge transfer (CT) can also occur between the donor and acceptor (Figure 1b).^{23–25} In this picture, the ET process is hampered by the CT dynamic, affecting the overall TTA-UC process and lowering the Φ_{UC} .

In the present work, we hypothesize that the issue of CT competing with ET in D-A dyads could be nullified if the CT state were contained within the donor fragment. With this in mind, (4-*N*-carbazolyl-2,6-dichlorophenyl)bis(2,4,6-trichlorophenyl)methyl radical (**TTM-Cz**) appeared as a promising donor for D-A dyads. First reported in 2006 by the Juliá group,²⁶ **TTM-Cz** is a stable radical adduct of the tris(2,4,6-trichlorophenyl)methyl radical (**TTM**) and carbazole (**Cz**). Previous studies on **TTM-Cz** and its derivatives led to the postulation that in the excited state, **TTM-Cz** can either emit ($D_1 \rightarrow D_0$) from its locally excited (LE) state or undergo structural reorganization following a CT, in the form of a twisted intramolecular charge transfer (TICT),²⁷ from the **Cz** moiety to the trivalent carbon atom in the **TTM** moiety (Figure 2a).^{26,28–30} For the above reasons, we concluded that **TTM-Cz** is a suitable donor that could be used to prevent photo-induced CT in a D-A dyad used for TTA-UC. Furthermore, **TTM-Cz** is also attractive for

circumventing the well-known singlet-to-triplet ISC. With **TTM-Cz**, one can directly perform doublet-to-triplet energy transfer (DTET), eliminating the need for ISC and the energy loss that comes with it (Figure 1c). Although the circumvention of ISC does not directly impact Φ_{UC} , it allows the process to be more energy efficient, which is important to the central idea of upconverting low-energy photons.

To date, DTET using **TTM**-based radicals has been demonstrated by several groups. Duan et al. used **TTM-Cz** as a donor to upconvert red light to blue or cyan light³¹ and in a similar manner, Yang et al. exploited the doublet photophysics of a triphenylamino-**TTM** derivative to achieve near-infrared TTA-UC with rubrene and perylene.³² Additionally, Friend et al. showed that rapid DTET can occur between **TTM-Cz** and anthracenes when linked together through the **Cz** moiety.³³

Figure 2. a) Optical transitions (absorption & emission) of **TTM-Cz** featuring CT characteristics in its excited doublet state. b) Doublet donor-acceptor dyads **TTM-Cz-Per** and **TTM-Cz-DPA** depicting the doublet energy donor (perylene = **Per** and 9,10-diphenylanthracene = **DPA**).

Herein, we report the synthesis and photophysical characterization of **TTM-Cz** based D-A dyads **TTM-Cz-Per** and **TTM-Cz-DPA** that use perylene (**Per**) and 9,10-diphenylanthracene (**DPA**) as the acceptors, respectively (Figure 2b). Using spectroscopic techniques and

computational tools, we aimed to determine the nature of the electronic interactions between **TTM-Cz** and the polyaromatic (PAH) acceptors (**Per** and **DPA**). Our investigations revealed that in the case of **TTM-Cz-Per**, there is rapid DTET from **TTM-Cz** to **Per** that is insensitive to molecular oxygen. Furthermore, without adding free acceptor chromophores, **TTM-Cz-Per** by itself is capable of performing red-to-blue TTA-UC regardless of the polarity of the media used or whether or not molecular oxygen is present. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first such example of an all-in-one D-A dyad that possesses such characteristics.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

All commercially obtained reagents and solvents were utilized without further purification. All spectroscopy measurements were performed using spectroscopy-grade solvents. EPR spectra were recorded on a Bruker[®] EMX EPR spectrometer.

2.1. Synthesis

Method A

Method B

Scheme 1. Synthesis of TTM-Cz based dyads TTM-Cz-Per and TTM-Cz-DPA. *Note: For Method B, TTM-Cz-Br was obtained by purification of the first step using 3-Bromocarbazole (similar to Method A), resulting in a mixture of the radical and nonradical precursor. This is why the Suzuki coupling gave a mixture of the radical and nonradical precursors.*

The synthesis and characterization of TTM-Cz, TTM-Cz-Per, and TTM-Cz-DPA, as well as their corresponding precursors, are detailed in the *Supporting Information* (Schemes S1–S8). Two different methods were employed for synthesizing the TTM-Cz compounds, as depicted in

Scheme 1. Method A follows previously reported protocols to prepare **TTM–Cz**,^{26,28} where radical **TTM** was linked to **Cz** in the presence of a base via a radical-mediated nucleophilic aromatic substitution. This produced a mixture of radical **TTM–Cz** and the nonradical counterpart which must be further oxidized (radicalized) to afford the desired radical **TTM–Cz**. Method B consists of Suzuki coupling of mono-brominated **TTM–Cz–Br** to borylated PAH (either **Per** or **DPA**) followed by oxidation (radical reaction) to give the desired radical dyads **TTM–Cz–Per** and **TTM–Cz–DPA**.

2.2. Computational Methods

Ground state geometry optimizations and spin density calculations of the $(D_0)(S_0)_A$ and $(D_0)(T_1)_A$ states were performed at the UB3LYP/6-31G(d,p) level of theory.³⁴ Vertical excitations to the $(D_1)_{LE}(S_0)_A$ state and the corresponding spin densities were computed with time-dependent density-functional theory (TD-DFT) using the Tamm-Dancoff approximation³⁵ and UCAM-B3LYP/6-31G(d,p)³⁶ after reoptimization at the same level of theory, as range separated hybrid functionals have shown high accuracy in the prediction of CT bands.³⁷ Solvation effects were included using the IEF-PCM model for hexane and THF. Further details are provided in the *Supporting Information*.

2.3. Photophysical Method & Photoluminescence Upconversion Procedure

UV–vis absorption spectra were recorded on an Ocean Optics® QEPRO-ABS spectrometer using a DH-mini light source. Emission spectra were recorded on an Edinburgh Instruments FLS1000 photoluminescence spectrometer. For power dependent measurements, the noncoherent Xe lamp of the FLS1000 spectrometer was used as the light source and a pinhole with a diameter

of 3 mm was placed in front of the sample. The intensity of the excitation light was varied using a variable neutral density filter. A 633 nm notch filter (NF633-25, Thorlabs) was placed in the emission path only for the power dependent measurements.

Transient absorption spectroscopy was carried out using an integrated Helios and EOS experimental apparatus from Ultrafast Systems. The apparatus utilizes a ytterbium femtosecond laser (Hyperion, Ultrafast Systems) with a fundamental at 1030 nm, a pulse duration of ~ 290 fs, and repetition rates of 2.14 kHz for the femtosecond experiments and 1.0 kHz for the nanosecond experiments. The pump beam was generated using a three-stage optical parametric amplifier (Apollo-Y, Ultrafast Systems) with pulse duration ranges from 100–400 fs. The femtosecond broadband probe extending between 360 and 500 nm was generated using the second harmonic of the Hyperion at 515 nm in a thin sapphire plate. A second broadband probe extending between 500 and 910 nm was generated using the laser fundamental, 1030 nm, in a 1 cm sapphire plate. Probe beams were steered through a Smart Delay Line (Ultrafast Systems) to scan the time domain with a delay window of ~ 7.5 ns and a minimum step size of ~ 3 fs. The nanosecond probe was generated using a separate supercontinuum laser (MOPA-based, Ultrafast Systems) with a pulse duration of ~ 0.75 ns. The pump-probe delay was generated electronically in the nanosecond transient absorption experiments. All probes were split into two separate beams, one of which was steered directly onto the reference detector while the other was steered through the sample compartment onto the signal detector. All samples were pumped with <85 nJ at 610 nm. Prior to the transient absorption measurements, all samples were dissolved in the proper solvent and the optical density (OD) was adjusted to 0.4–0.6 in a 2 mm path-length quartz cuvette. The sample solutions were then degassed through four cycles of a freeze-pump-thaw process to remove dissolved oxygen.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1. EPR Data

Figure 3. (a) EPR spectra of **TTM-Cz**, **TTM-Cz-Per**, and **TTM-Cz-DPA** in toluene at room temperature and (b) methylcyclohexane (MCH) at 77 K. *Note: These spectra were recorded in normal toluene solvents (not degassed).*

To ascertain the open-shell characteristics of the **TTM-Cz** sensitizer and **TTM-Cz-Per/DPA** dyads, we performed EPR experiments in toluene at room temperature and methylcyclohexane at 77 K, as shown in Figures 3a and 3b, respectively. All three compounds show single featureless broadband profiles at room temperature, whereas at 77 K, complex hyperfine coupling was observed. These results confirm that the radical nature of the **TTM-Cz** sensitizer was also present in **TTM-Cz-Per/DPA** dyads.

3.2. Absorption and Emission Spectroscopy

Figure 4. UV-vis profiles of **TTM-Cz**, **TTM-Cz-Per**, and **TTM-Cz-DPA** recorded in (a) toluene and (b) 30% v/v DCM:EtOH.

The UV-vis absorption spectra for **TTM-Cz** and the **TTM-Cz-Per/DPA** dyads in toluene and DCM:EtOH (30% v/v) are shown in Figure 4. For all three compounds, there are distinctive features that can be ascribed to intrinsic $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions below 500 nm and a CT band centered at ca. 600 nm. Specifically, for the **Per** and **DPA** dyads, the high-energy bands at ca. 400 nm correspond to the convoluted transitions from the **TTM-Cz** and acceptors moieties. The energy of this band appears to be insensitive to both solvent polarity and **Cz** substitution. In contrast, the weak lower energy band in the 600–630 nm range is seemingly sensitive to the solvent polarity and the PAH substituent. The absorption profiles undergo a blueshift when moving from toluene to DCM:EtOH (30% v/v). This suggests that nonpolar solvents can stabilize the LE excited state or otherwise reduce the SOMO-LUMO/SUMO gap. Compared to the profile of **TTM-Cz**, the absorption profile of **TTM-Cz-Per/DPA** dyads revealed a bathochromic shift in toluene. This

was also observed by Friend et al. when anthracenes were substituted onto **Cz**.³³ The shift in absorption wavelength can be attributed to PAHs acting as electron-donating, raising the energy level of the SOMO. It is also worth noting that in the case of **TTM-Cz-Per**, additional absorption features are present at ca. 425 and 450 nm. These can be attributed to the transitions in **Per**. With this in mind, it was decided that for all studies concerning DTET, the λ_{Exc} should be ≥ 600 nm to selectively excite the **TTM-Cz** moiety.

Figure 5. Singlet oxygen $^1\Delta_g(\text{O}_2)$ photoluminescence generated from aerated solution of **TTM-Cz-Per** at various ODs at $\lambda_{\text{Exc}} = 610$ nm; inset shows the non-emissive profile for a toluene solution of **TTM-Cz**.

To establish whether DTET occurs from **TTM-Cz** to **Per** in **TTM-Cz-Per**, aerated solutions of **TTM-Cz-Per** at various concentrations were excited at $\lambda_{\text{Exc}} = 610$ nm, and emission profiles were recorded in the range of 1250–1300 nm. As shown in Figure 5, $^1\Delta_g(\text{O}_2)$ phosphorescence emission was detected at ~ 1275 nm. On the other hand, the aerated toluene solution of **TTM-Cz** did not produce this same emission (Figure 5 inset) thus it can be concluded that the excited triplet state of **Per**, $^3(\text{Per})^*$, in the **TTM-Cz-Per** dyad can be quenched readily by molecular oxygen up

to some extent. Based on this finding, we later verified the stability of the **DPA** dyad under ambient conditions. It is well-documented that acenes, such as anthracenes and **DPA** would react with $^1\text{O}_2$ via a [4+2]-cycloaddition reaction. Expectedly, aerated solutions of **TTM-Cz-DPA** showed gradual photobleaching or photooxidation when kept under ambient light. For this reason, it was decided to focus further studies on **TTM-Cz-Per** dyad, which would be easier to handle under ambient conditions. Also, with this finding, it is worth cautioning that a recent report by Friend et al.³³ on **TTM-Cz-Acenes** qubit systems may undergo photooxidation if used under ambient conditions, however this was not addressed in their report.

Figure 6. Steady-state emission under ambient conditions of (a) **TTM-Cz** and (b) **TTM-Cz-Per** in DCM:EtOH (30% v/v) and toluene. Emission under deaerated conditions of (c) **TTM-Cz** and (d) **TTM-Cz-Per** in DCM:EtOH (30% v/v) and toluene.

Table 1. UV-vis and photoluminescence characteristics of **TTM-Cz** and **TTM-Cz-Per**.

Entry	Compound	Solvent	λ_{Abs}	ϵ	λ_{Em}	τ_{Ambient}^b	τ_{FPPT}^b
			(nm) ^a	(M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹) ^a	(nm) ^b	(μ s)	(μ s)
1	TTM-Cz	Toluene	606	2995.2	686	9.59 ^c	9.43 ^c
2		DCM:EtOH (30% v/v)	600	3206.9	800	-	-
3	TTM-Cz-Per	Toluene	627	5200.2	695	9.39 ^d	9.34 ^d
4						9.26 ^c	9.27 ^c
5						9.03 ^e	9.20 ^e
6		DCM:EtOH (30% v/v)	602	4449.5	-	-	-
7	TTM-Cz + Per	Toluene	-	-	-	9.30 ^f	9.86 ^f
8						9.92 ^c	9.80 ^c

^a Measurements were done in solvent under ambient conditions. ^b Samples were excited at $\lambda_{\text{Exc}} = 610$ nm with OD = 0.1. For the values of λ_{Em} , the results are the same regardless of if the samples are deaerated or not. ^c $\lambda_{\text{Em}} = 690$ nm. ^d $\lambda_{\text{Em}} = 480$ nm. ^e $\lambda_{\text{Em}} = 850$ nm. ^f $\lambda_{\text{Em}} = 475$ nm. For **TTM-Cz + Per**, the molar ratio was 1:2.4.

The emission spectra for **TTM-Cz** and **TTM-Cz-Per** in toluene and DCM:EtOH (30% v/v) under ambient and oxygen-free conditions are shown in Figure 6. Interestingly, substituting **Per** onto the **Cz** moiety led to a slight redshift of ca. 10 nm and a significant decrease in intensity when comparing to **TTM-Cz** in toluene. Also, as illustrated in Figure 6a, a redshift and a significant decrease in emission intensity was observed for both **TTM-Cz** and **TTM-Cz-Per** in DCM:EtOH (30% v/v) compared to the profiles in toluene. The quenching is more pronounced with **TTM-**

Cz-Per as the intrinsic emission of the **TTM-Cz** moiety completely vanished. These findings are in agreement with those of the Juliá group,²⁸ where emission intensity was greater in nonpolar solvents than in polar media, and electron-donating substituents on the **Cz** moiety caused a redshift in the emission band. This supports the hypothesis that there is an intramolecular CT from the **Cz** moiety to the radical-centered carbon atom of **TTM**; despite this, the significant decrease in intensity of the intrinsic emission of **TTM-Cz** in **TTM-Cz-Per** can also be partly attributed to quenching of the doublet excited state of **TTM-Cz** via $^2(\text{TTM-Cz})^* \rightarrow \text{Per}$ DTET to produce the $^3(\text{Per})^*$ species.

In addition to the red photoluminescence, a blue-green emission centered at ca. 490 nm was detected for samples of **TTM-Cz-Per**, and this emission was present regardless of solvent polarity or the presence of oxygen, as shown in Figures 6b and 6d. Figure 7a reveals that the intensity of this higher-energy emission band quickly diminished as the solution concentration of **TTM-Cz-Per** was increased. The reduction in emission intensity can be ascribed to the secondary inner filter effect, as this emission overlaps with the absorption profile of **TTM-Cz-Per**. When the solution concentration was kept constant while varying the power density of the excitation light, the intensity of the emission showed a quadratic behavior, as shown in Figures 7b and 7c. This is characteristic of the non-linearity of the TTA-UC process.^{5,7,14,18,38-40} Based on this finding, we attributed the emission band at ca. 420–600 nm to the delayed fluorescence of **Per** as the result of TTA between two $^3(\text{Per})^*$ species of **TTM-Cz-Per**.

Figure 7. a) Delayed emission/fluorescence of **Per** at varying concentrations of **TTM-Cz-Per**; inset shows the integrated intensity of the emission at various concentrations. b) Power density-dependent delayed fluorescence of **Per** from red-excitation ($\lambda_{\text{Exc}} = 620 \text{ nm}$) of **TTM-Cz-Per**. c) Quadratic response of the delayed fluorescence of **Per** vs. excitation power density for solutions of **TTM-Cz-Per** under both ambient and oxygen-free conditions. d) Absorbance at 376 nm (inset: 610 nm) for toluene solutions of **TTM-Cz** and **TTM-Cz-Per** that were continuously irradiated with red light for 24 hours ($\lambda_{\text{Exc}} = 620 \text{ nm}$, power = 2.23 mW, $[\text{TTM-Cz}] = 38 \mu\text{M}$, $[\text{TTM-Cz-Per}] = 22 \mu\text{M}$). *Note: For the power density-dependent measurements, a noncoherent Xe lamp was used as the excitation source with a 3 mm diameter pinhole directly in front of the sample. Power density was adjusted using a variable neutral density filter.*

Using a relative method, we estimated the $\Phi_{\text{UC}} \approx 0.012\%$ for a sample of OD = 0.021 excited with the non-coherent xenon lamp at $\lambda_{\text{Exc}} = 610 \text{ nm}$ (for more details, see Supporting Information,

Figure S18). Based on the above result, we postulated that as the **TTM-Cz** fragment of the dyad was selectively excited at 610 nm, the **Per** acceptor was promoted to the triplet excited state via DTET, i.e. $(D_1)_{\text{TTM-Cz}} (S_0)_{\text{Per}} \rightarrow (D_0)_{\text{TTM-Cz}} (T_1)_{\text{Per}}$. This is also supported by the fact that the intensity of the red emission from **TTM-Cz-Per** is significantly reduced compared to that of **TTM-Cz** which would be the result of the DTET process quenching the doublet excited state of the **TTM-Cz** moiety. Since there is no noticeable difference in upconversion efficiency between nonpolar and polar solvents, we hypothesize that the DTET could occur from either the LE or CT state of **TTM-Cz**.

Also, it is noteworthy to mention that the upconversion efficiency appears to be negligibly affected by oxygen, a finding that is unprecedented for TTA-UC. In addition, TTA-UC occurred without adding free **Per** acceptors to the samples. This is another unprecedented finding because, to our knowledge, all previous reports on D-A dyads for TTA-UC required the addition of a free acceptor for the upconversion process to be observed.^{20,22,23,25,41}

Further, as tabulated in Table 1, entries 1 and 3, we observed that **TTM-Cz-Per** has similar emission decay kinetics at 690 nm as **TTM-Cz** in toluene. This can be explained by the fact that although the two components exhibit different multiplicities (doublet and triplet), they act as a two-in-one chromophore. On the other hand, we observed that the kinetics associated with the emission decay in the control sample of **TTM-Cz + Per** (Table 1) appeared longer, indicating that in the **TTM-Cz-Per** dyad, the DTET is primarily intramolecular. Also, in both **TTM-Cz-Per** and **TTM-Cz + Per**, the emission decay at 475–480 nm is longer in deaerated solutions when compared to solutions under ambient conditions. This is not surprising as in deaerated samples, quenching of the T_1 state of **Per** is precluded.

We also investigated the stability a toluene solution of **TTM-Cz-Per** under continuous irradiation (at 620 nm, 2.23 mW) over a period of 24 h. As shown in Figure 7d, this dyad is noticeably stable than **TTM-Cz**. This result agrees with previous findings by Albrecht et al., who demonstrated that additional substitution on the carbazole moiety with a phenyl ring significantly enhances photostability.^{42,43}

3.3. Transient Absorption Spectroscopy

To further explore the DTET process and understand the nature of the excited state and/or transients, we performed femtosecond and nanosecond transient absorption (fs-TA and ns-TA, respectively) spectroscopy on oxygen-free solutions of **TTM-Cz**, **TTM-Cz-Per**, and a mixture of **TTM-Cz** and **Per** (1:2.4 molar ratio). The combined fs-ns-TA results are shown in Figure 8 (see *Supporting Information* Figures S20 and S21 for the individual fs-TA and ns-TA data, respectively). The doublet transient of **TTM-Cz**, $^2(\text{TTM-Cz})^*$, absorbs from 500 to ca. 900 nm with a maximum at ca. 570 nm (Figures 8a,b). A negative absorption band appearing between 600 and 750 nm is the combination of the ground-state bleach and stimulated emission, centered at ca. 630 and ca. 690 nm, respectively. Since it was hypothesized that the doublet excited state of **TTM-Cz** features LE and CT states^{26,28-30}, we ascribed the maximum at ca. 570 nm to be the LE $D_1 \rightarrow D_n$ transition and the broad absorption at ca. 850 nm to be associated with the CT transient. The LE transient band was fitted with a biexponential function to produce two lifetime constants, $\tau_1 = 152$ ps and $\tau_2 = 21.47$ ns; whereas the CT transient generated a monoexponential decay with $\tau = 24.39$ ns (Figure 8c and Table 2). Interestingly, these transient species are also present in the mixture of **TTM-Cz + Per**; however, they have much shorter lifetime values, with $\tau_1 = 139$ ps and $\tau_2 = 13.65$ ns for the LE transient, and $\tau = 13.93$ ns for the CT transient (Figures 8g-i). For the **TTM-Cz +**

Per sample, we attributed the shorter lifetimes to be a result of ${}^2(\text{TTM-Cz})^* \rightarrow \text{Per}$ DTET leading to the quenching of the excited state of **TTM-Cz**.

Figure 8. (a & b) Transient absorption map and spectra for **TTM-Cz** and the corresponding kinetic traces (c). (d & e) Transient absorption map and spectra for **TTM-Cz-Per** and the corresponding kinetic traces (f). (g & h) Transient absorption map and spectra for **TTM-Cz + Per** (1:2.4 molar ratio) and the corresponding kinetic traces (i). *Note: Insets for the kinetic traces are the kinetic traces with a logarithmic time scale.*

Furthermore, an additional long-lived transient species with absorption centered at 490 nm can be attributed to the triplet transient of **Per**, $^3\text{Per}^*$. This species decays with a biexponential kinetic with time constants $\tau_1 = 13.40$ ns and $\tau_2 = 5.98$ μs (Figures 8g–i and Table 2). The τ_1 component was assigned to the residual doublet transient of **TTM–Cz**, which overlaps with the spectrum of $^3\text{Per}^*$. This is supported by the fact that τ_1 at 490 nm is almost equal to τ_2 at 570 nm for the decay of the LE transient of **TTM–Cz** in the **TTM–Cz + Per** sample. The long-lived component with τ_2 is attributed to the decay of $^3\text{Per}^*$, as relaxation to the S_0 ground state is a spin-forbidden process.

Table 2. Transients time constants for **TTM–Cz**, **TTM–Cz–Per**, and **TTM–Cz + Per** (1:2.4 molar ratio).

Compound	λ_{Abs} (nm)	τ_1 (ns)	τ_2 (ns)
TTM–Cz	570	0.152 (25.3%)	21.47 (74.7%)
	850	24.39	-
TTM–Cz–Per	570	8.73 (81.1%)	97.06 (18.9%)
	810	4.31	-
TTM–Cz + Per	490	13.40 (49.5%)	5980 (50.5%)
	570	0.139 (38.3%)	13.65 (61.7%)
	850	13.93	-

For **TTM–Cz–Per**, the transient absorption band stretched from 500 to 900 nm with apparent maxima at ca. 570 and 810 nm (Figures 8d,e). As in **TTM–Cz**, the transient species with absorptions at 570 and 810 nm can be attributed to the LE and CT states of the **TTM–Cz** moiety, respectively. However, it is likely that the absorption feature of the triplet transient of **Per**, $^3\text{Per}^*$, partially overlaps with the broad peak near 570 nm. Expectedly, the fitting of the band centered at ca. 570 nm gave a biexponential kinetic with time constants $\tau_1 = 8.73$ ns and $\tau_2 = 97.06$ ns (Figure

8f and Table 2). The τ_1 component was attributed to the decay of the LE transient of **TTM-Cz** component in the dyad, which, like **TTM-Cz + Per** sample, has a shorter lifetime due to DTET from **TTM-Cz** to **Per**. The long-lived τ_2 component is likely the decay of $^3\text{Per}^*$; however, it is worth noting that the lifetime is significantly shorter than what was observed in the mixture of **TTM-Cz + Per**. This can be explained by a likely intramolecular back energy transfer from $^3\text{Per}^*$ to **TTM-Cz**. Furthermore, the decay of the CT transient band at ca. 810 nm was fitted with a monoexponential function to produce a time constant of $\tau = 4.31$ ns, which was attributed to the residual of the CT transient from the **TTM-Cz** component.

Furthermore, the LE transient species from **TTM-Cz** and **TTM-Cz-Per** exhibit unrelated characteristics that deserve to be mentioned. In **TTM-Cz**, the transient species grows rapidly before decaying biexponentially, whereas in **TTM-Cz-Per**, within the 350-fs time resolution of the instrument, the transient species has an initial rapid growth followed by a quick/sharp decay (Figure 8f). This decay is followed by a slower growth that turns into a complete biexponential decay (*See Supporting Information, Figures S20 & S21*). We postulate that this complex dynamic is likely due to the LE state of **TTM-Cz** being populated, followed by a rapid intramolecular DTET to **Per** and the growth of $^3\text{Per}^*$, which formed simultaneously as the $^2(\text{TTM-Cz})^*$ decayed.

It is worth noting that the DTET dynamic was not clearly observed for either **TTM-Cz-Per** or **TTM-Cz + Per** (decay of doublet transient of $^2(\text{TTM-Cz})^*$ accompanied by growth of $^3\text{Per}^*$); this is most likely due to the overlap between the transient bands of **TTM-Cz** and the triplet transient spectrum of **Per**. Alternatively, it is possible that DTET may occur at a rate beyond the resolution of the instrumentation used.

3.4. Computational Investigations

To ascertain the spin state and overall spin density within the **TTM-Cz-Per/DPA** dyads, we calculated the spin density maps in the doublet $(D_0)(S_0)_A$, $(D_1)_{LE}(S_0)_A$ ($S = 1/2$) and quartet $(D_0)(T_1)_A$ ($S = 3/2$) states of **TTM-Cz**, **TTM-Cz-Per**, and **TTM-Cz-DPA** as shown in Figure 9. In the $(D_0)(S_0)_A$ state, the spin density maps for all three chromophores have an unpaired electron localized over the **TTM** fragment. The three compounds share an absorption band at ~ 400 nm that we attribute to $(D_1)_{LE}(S_0)_A$ and characterize as a local excitation of the common **TTM-Cz** moiety (see Natural Transition Orbitals in Figure S22). In this state, the unpaired electron delocalizes over the **Cz** moiety. These results suggest that after excitation to the $(D_1)_{LE}(S_0)_A$ state, these dyads could exhibit the expected intramolecular DTET from **TTM-Cz** to **Per** and **DPA** to generate the corresponding $^3\text{Per}^*$ and $^3\text{DPA}^*$, respectively. This is further corroborated by spin densities computed in the $(D_0)(T_1)_A$ state showing a net density of unpaired electrons of $\rho \approx 1$ on the **TTM-Cz** donor and of $\rho \approx 2$ on the acceptor. Photoluminescence from $^1\Delta_g(\text{O}_2)$ and/or observation of the delayed fluorescence from the **TTM-Cz-Per** sample, presumably from the $^3\text{Per}^*$, further corroborate the computational results and our hypothesis of intramolecular DTET.

Figure 9. Spin density maps of the $(D_0)(S_0)_A$, $(D_1)_{LE}(S_0)_A$, and $(D_0)(T_1)_A$ states computed in the gas phase for **TTM-Cz**, **TTM-Cz-Per**, and **TTM-Cz-DPA**. Partial spin densities per fragment (ρ) were normalized so that total densities are $\rho = 1$ and $\rho = 3$ for doublet and quartet states, respectively. $(D_1)_{LE}(S_0)_A$ corresponds to the first allowed transition (nonzero oscillator strength): Root = 1, $\lambda_{abs} = 428$ nm for **TTM-Cz**; Root = 2, $\lambda_{abs} = 433$ nm for **TTM-Cz-Per**; Root = 2, $\lambda_{abs} = 431$ nm for **TTM-Cz-DPA**.

CONCLUSIONS:

The current study demonstrates the first example of all-in-one D-A dyads that can perform TTA-UC under ambient conditions and without the need for additional acceptor/annihilator molecules to be present in the matrix. In the case of the **TTM-Cz-Per** dyad, detection of $^1\Delta_g(O_2)$ emission and upconverted photoluminescence confirmed DTET from the **TTM-Cz** moiety to the **Per** acceptor. In addition, the fact that upconverted photoluminescence was seemingly unaffected by solvent polarity suggests that the DTET process can occur from both the LE and CT states of the **TTM-Cz** moiety.

Using time-resolved transient absorption spectroscopy, we observed ultrafast intramolecular interactions between the **TTM-Cz** donor and the **Per** acceptor in **TTM-Cz-Per**. Spin density computations corroborate this finding as the spin density map of the $(D_0)(T_1)_A$ state of **TTM-Cz-Per** indicates that an unpaired electron becomes delocalized over the **Per** moiety, which is consistent with **Per** being in the triplet excited state. On the other hand, the intermolecular DTET in the sample of free **TTM-Cz + Per** was an inefficient process. The current results highlight the possibility of designing single-component D-A systems for light-harvesting and photon upconversion processes. Furthermore, we demonstrated that it is possible to deconvolute competing ET and CT dynamics in the D-A systems. Currently, we are devising related multichromophoric systems that can potentially be used for other non-linear photon-management processes in next-generation optoelectronic devices.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT:

Supporting Information: The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.10XX/jacs.XXXXX>. Materials and general methods, synthesis and characterization including NMR of all compounds, additional steady-state and transient spectroscopic characterization, computational data, and structures optimization details (PDF).

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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